

YAPON BEHISI – *CHAENOMELES JAPONICA* (THUNB.) LINDL. EX SPACH NING TARQALISH AREALLARI VA BIOEKOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Yapon behisi – *Chaenomeles japonica* (Thunb.) Lindl. ex Spach ning tarqalish areallari va bioekologik xususiyatlari bo‘yicha ma‘lumotlar keltirilgan. *Chaenomeles japonica* ning tabiiy tarqalish hududlari / vatani – Janubiy Koreya, Yaponiya (Xonsyu, Kyushu). Ushbu tur dunyoning ko‘plab mamlakatlarida introduksiya qilingan istiqbolli o‘simlikdir. Yapon behisining yillik global ishlab chiqarilishi 0,7 million tonnani tashkil etadi. Oxirgi yillarda yapon behisi mevasi hosildorligi oshganiga qaramay, hosilni yig‘ishning turli yillaridagi kimyoviy tarkibining o‘zgarishi to‘g‘risidagi ma‘lumotlar hali ham cheklangan. Yapon behi urug‘idagi yog‘ miqdori va uning turli yillarda yig‘ib olingan mevalardan olingan profili (turli xil abiotik omillar kombinatsiyasining ta‘sirini) hali o‘rganilmagan. Shu sababli, ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarimizda turli yillardagi yapon behisi navining urug‘ moylari tarkibidagi yog‘ miqdori va sifatiga turli tuproq-iqlim omillarining ta‘sirini aniqlash ishlarini olib borilmoqda.

Kalit so‘zlar: *Chaenomeles japonica*, tarqalish areallari, bioekologik xususiyatlari, foydalanish istiqbollari.

Yapon behisi – *Chaenomeles japonica* (Thunb.) Lindl. ex Spach Rosaceae oilasiga mansub, hayotiy shakliga ko‘ra buta bo‘lib, asosan mo‘tadil biomlarda o‘sadi. Turning tabiiy tarqalish hududlari / vatani – Janubiy Koreya, Yaponiya (Xonsyu, Kyushu). Ushbu tur dunyoning ko‘plab mamlakatlarida introduksiya qilingan (POWO, 2024) istiqbolli o‘simlikdir (**1-rasm**).

1-rasm. *Chaenomeles japonica* ning (yashil rangda) tabiiy tarqalgan va (binafsha rangda) introduksiya qilingan areallari (POWO, 2024)

2-rasm. *Chaenomeles japonica* ning mevasining ko‘rinishi
(T.X. Makhkamov olgan sur‘at)

Chaenomeles japonica asosan sharbatlar (Ros va boshq., 2004), murabbo (Wojdyło va boshq., 2008) va qiyomlar kabi oziq-ovqat va ichimliklar ishlab chiqarish uchun yetishtiriladigan mevali ekindir (Seglina va boshqalar, 2009). O‘zbekiston sharoitida Yapon behisi asosan bog‘ va parklarda manzarali buta sifatida ekib kelinadi (3-rasm).

3-rasm. *Chaenomeles japonica* ning gullash davridagi ko‘rinishi
(Sh. G‘ulomkhadjaeva olgan sur‘at)

O‘zbekiston sharoitida *Chaenomeles japonica* ning mevalari va urug‘lari morfologiyasi (G‘ulomkhadjaeva, 2023), undan Toshkent shahrini ko‘kamlardarishda foydalanish (G‘ulomkhadjaeva, 2022) bo‘yicha ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari olib borilgan.

Yapon behisining yillik global ishlab chiqarilishi 0,7 million tonnani tashkil etadi (FAOSTAT, 2019), shuning uchun turning plantatsiyalarini tashkil etish ishlarida urug‘dan foydalanish iqtisodiy va ekologik nuqtai nazardan muhimdir. Yog‘ ishlab chiqarish uchun yapon behisining urug‘idan hosil bo‘lgan qo‘shimcha mahsulotlarning tarkibi muqobil foydalanish uchun kalit hisoblanadi. Yapon behisi urug‘idan olingan yog‘ bir to‘yinmagan (C18:1 ning 30-40%) va ko‘p to‘yinmagan (C18:2 ning 40-50%) yog‘ kislotalarining qimmatli manbai ekanligi aniqlangan (Urbanavičičiūtė va boshq., 2019), a-tokoferol (Mišina va boshq., 2020), karotenoidlar, skualen va b-sitosterollar (Górnaś va Rudzińska, 2016). Meva sanoati tomonidan ishlab chiqarilgan qo‘shimcha mahsulotlardan (urug‘lar va yadrolar) neftni qayta ishlash uchun potentsial foydalanish atrof-muhit, sog‘liq va iqtisodiy jihatdan foydali ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi (Górnaś va Rudzińska, 2016). Noan‘anaviy o‘simlik moylari bioaktiv birikmalarning qimmatli manbai bo‘lib, ularning tarkibi o‘simlik turlari va navlari kabi ko‘plab omillarga bog‘liq (Górnaś va boshq., 2019). Urug‘larning yetuklik bosqichi (Mišina va boshq., 2020), abiotik omillar, quritish shart-sharoitlari, moy olishdan oldin urug‘larga issiqlik bilan ishlov berish va moy olish usuli va

uning parametrlari (Rękas va boshq., 2018). Oxirgi yillarda yapon behisi mevasi hosildorligi oshganiga qaramay, hosilni yig‘ishning turli yillaridagi kimyoviy tarkibining o‘zgarishi to‘g‘risidagi ma’lumotlar hali ham cheklangan. Yapon behisi urug‘idagi yog‘ miqdori va uning turli yillarda yig‘ib olingan mevalardan olingan profili (turli xil abiotik omillar kombinatsiyasining ta’siri) hali o‘rganilmagan. Shu sababli, ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarimizda turli yillardagi yapon behisining urug‘ moylari tarkibidagi yog‘ miqdori va sifatiga turli tuproq-iqlim omillarining ta’sirini aniqlash ishlarini olib bormoqdamiz.

Yapon behisi – *Chaenomeles japonica* hozirda Shimoliy Yevropa uchun potentsial mevali ekin sifatida qaralmoqda. Yangi hosilni muvaffaqiyatli joriy etish uchun tez va arzon ko‘paytirish usullari muhim hisoblanadi. *Chaenomeles japonica* ni generativ ko‘paytirish oson, lekin ushbu turning navlari urug‘lar orqali haqiqiy nasl bermaydi. Navlarni o‘z xususiyatlarini saqlab qolish uchun vegetativ tarzda ko‘paytirish kerak (Rumpunen 2002). *Chaenomeles japonica* ni yillik yashil (yumshoq, yog‘ochlashmagan) novdalaridan qalamchalar tayyorlab ko‘paytirilishi mumkin (Kviklys & Rumpunen 1996), qattiq yog‘ochlashgan novdalaridan ko‘paytirish esa nisbatan samarasiz xisoblanadi (Ratomskyte 1990). Shu bilan birga tuplarni bo‘lish yo‘li bilan ham ko‘paytirish mumkin, lekin ushbu usuldan foydalangan holda keng miqyosda plantatsiyalarni hosil qilish iqtisodiy jihatdan samarali hisoblanmaydi. *Chaenomeles japonica* ni mikroklonal ko‘paytirishda mikrokesimlarning ildiz otishi qiyin kechadi (Panavas 1994) va in vitro sharoitida ko‘payish darajasi Rosaceae oilasi ichidagi boshqa turlarning ko‘payish tezligiga nisbatan past hisoblanadi (Norton va Boe 1982).

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